

From Outer Space to the Great Ocean's Depths: An Adventure in High Performance Composite Materials

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ABSTRACT

More and more industrial branches are concerned by composite materials today. AEROSPATIALE began its activities in this field in the 60's. This industrial gamble started in the high performance area to meet the payload requirements of the French space and ballistic systems. If the resistance to fatigue cycles and to notch propagation much higher than those obtained with metals as well as remarkable chemical inertia were also profitable to these systems, these characteristics are keys ones for the extra aeronautical applications.

Today, AEROSPATIALE Aquitaine has produced more than 2 000 filament wound structures and among them 650 motor cases. It had developed automatic systems to industrially manufacture multidirectional composite materials (nd silica phenolic, Carbon-carbon, carbon-phenolic, composite ceramics) to fabricate reentry bodies, rocket motor nozzles, casings, etc.

In the extra aeronautical domains, numerous areas are covered such as gas and energy storage, marine activities, transportations, human prosthesis, etc.

INTRODUCTION

From the very beginning our world has known the composite materials. Indeed, the trees are made with this material : fibers linked together by an adherent. Wood was used very early for its remarkable strength over weight ratio and its chemical inertness to build small boats for example. Its resistance to notch propagation was also profitable to arms and tool. When the aeronautical era arrived these characteristics were a big help for aviation pioneers and wood is still used to build parts of small airplanes. But the stringent requirements of the ballistic and space systems asked for an improvement of the characteristics of both the fibers and the adherent (named also the matrix). At the same time new manufacturing procedures needed to be invented in order to respect the anisotropy of the material. In order to lower the cost of the parts produced and to insure a better reliability and reproductibility, automation is now entering more and more this field.

Due to its aerospace background from the beginning AEROSPATIALE was quite involved in the composite materials challenge. As part of the Space and Ballistic System Division of AEROSPATIALE, the Aquitaine plant located near Bordeaux devotes about one half of its 2,000 person work force to the design, the fabrication, the quality control and the qualification of products made with high performance composite materials. The following sections will briefly outline some of our achievements for the French ballistic and space systems as well as some products which make use of space technology which have been applied to different domains, including marine activities at a depth of 3,000 meters.

THE FILAMENT WOUND PRODUCTS

In the early sixties the filament winding technique was introduced in FRANCE by SUD-AVIATION one of the future partners of AEROSPATIALE who manufactures motor cases. The first application of this technology was made for the DIAMANT A civil launcher of which the first launching in 1965 was a great success. Indeed, the second stage, for which we had the responsibility of the entire structure including the nozzle, was composed of a glass epoxy filament wound case. From that time, about 650 motor cases (up to 2000 mm in diameter and 2500 mm in length) were manufactured and more than 1,000 small pressure vessels designed to study the resin composition, the fibers (glass, boron, carbon, aramid) and the winding pattern. This could not be done without developing powerful means in the field of :

- the manufacturing process (filament winding machines up to 8 m of useful length) which is more and more computerized now,
- the design and calculation (computer aided design and finite element calculation),
- the laboratory studies for new fabrication and control processes - the qualification tests (means to pressurize up to 1800 bars and to record the measurements on 240 channels). All this high technology level could not always stay only in the aerospace field ; it had to enter other sectors of activity. This era is now open and our industrial policy leads to technology transfers in other fields, if necessary.

Figure 1 : The Kevlar * 402, a qualified case for the second stage of the M4 missile

* Kevlar : trade mark of the Dupont de Nemours aramid fibers

Figure 2 : Satellite filament winding machine used for prepreg tapes

Figure 3 : Glass composite cylinders

We have studied a range of composite cylinders (3 to 31.4 liters). This cylinders are manufactured according to the design of an aluminium alloy liner wrapped by a filament wound glass epoxy composite. The metallic liner is used as a mandrel during the manufacturing process and also to assure gastightness ; this liner also shares a small amount of the mechanical strength. The composite structure was designed to allow a safety factor of 3 with respect to the service pressure. These cylinders are about 3 times lighter than their metallic equivalents and have a fatigue resistance superior to 50,000 pressure cycles. They are presently investigated by the French governmental agency in charge of pressure vessels. Other designs were also studied : for example, the use of rubber liners and very high performance fibers such as the aramid fibers. If the characteristics of such cylinders are higher, their price is also higher due to the to day price of the fibers. Consequently this type of design will be selected when the cost saving in operation induced by the weight saving is rather large.

Figure 4 : A composite flywheel

There are different methods to store energy. One of them uses the kinetic energy of a rotor suspended in a vacuum by magnetic bearings. It's a clean and quite reversible method. Such systems were developed service in a telephone exchange in Rochefort-en-Yvelines. It is capable of delivering 3 kW during 20 minutes in case of electricity shortage. In using a composite flywheel the energy stored by unit mass can be multiplied by a factor up to 5 in comparison with the metallic version. The rim is made with carbon and glass designed in such a way that there is a deformation compatibility on the interface. Composite spokes join this rim to the boss which is attached to the magnetic bearing system. Such a flywheel is designed to allow a peripheral speed of 800 m/s which means a gravity acceleration of 160,000 g.

The first test was conducted up to 730 m/s. Let's not forget that a rotor made with the best steel cannot exceed a speed of 560 m/s at the periphery.

The preceding examples made use of the exceptional resistance/weight ratio of high performance composite materials. In addition, marine activities require chemical inertia. This was applied some-time ago when a glass composite cylindrical structure was stored for five years in the Cherbourg harbour and subjected to the tide activity without corrosion. This type of structure is studied in order to manufacture a cover for the under water equipment. A carbon version of this cylindrical structures collapsed at a pressure of 100 bars (the equivalent of 1000 meters of water). The structures weighed 16 kg the metallic equivalent would have weighed 40 kilos. There is an obvious advantage for the transportation of the system in the air in a marine workfield. We are studying to day a new version collapsing at 800 bars. The first results are quite good.

Another application, that we are now investigating, is the manufacturing of composite pipes for offshore petroleum research and production platforms which weigh 3 to 4 times less than their metallic equivalents.

THE CONTINUOUS FIBER MULTIDIRECTIONAL STRUCTURES

There are cases where the 2 D composite materials suffer delamination. This is true when the processing involves high temperature treatments (within the range of 600°C to 3000°C) and/or when the structures being used are subjected to very high thermomechanical agressions.

Figure 5 : Cylindrical instrument container in carbon epoxy composite

Figure 6 : SEM image of 3 D carbon-carbon

Figure 7 : 3 D automatic weaving loom

In these circumstances multidirectional composite materials must be used. Those made with continuous fibers are the most resistant. AEROSPATIALE studies and industrially produces products made with kevlar, carbon, silica and other ceramic fibers impregnated with resin and ceramic matrices. As an example we will talk about 3 D carbon-carbon structures having a hollow polar shape.

Our work in this field started in 1968 in cooperation with the French company LE CARBONE LORRAINE. This mutual effort, linked with those undertaken with several industrial or university laboratories wellknown in the field, was recently transformed into an industrial agreement creating a new range of carbon-carbon composites : the AEROLOR. Such materials are normally done in two phases : the preform manufacturing corresponding to the fibers' alignment in three directions and the densification corresponding to the infiltration of the carbon matrix in the preform.

Figure 8 : The 3D carbon-carbon manufacturing workshop

top, hoop and radial yarns are automatically installed. If necessary, a shaping tool can bend the rods during this part of the process in order to obtain a contoured preform at the end. Then, the metallic rods are automatically replaced by yarns. The densification of the preform by a carbon matrix is undertaken, by successive cycles of impregnation with pitch, carbonisation at 1,000 bars 650°C and graphitization at 2600°C. This process involves many steps with high level of technology equipment that needs to be checked carefully on a 24 hours bases. That's the reason why all the machines are computerized. Moreover, a general control panel monitors all of them and generates the quality control sheets for each part produced.

In order to lower the cost and to insure better reliability and reproductibility these steps have been automatized and are undertaken in a very modern workshop.

To weave automatically 3 D preforms, AEROSPATIALE has developed an automatic process patented en FRANCE and in many countries of the world. This process basically consists of installing vertical metallic rods maintained in the correct positions by pierced plates. These metallic rods simulate the future longitudinal direction of the preform. This network is then placed in the loom and is constantly rotating. From the bottom to the

Figure 9 : Blank of 3D carbon-carbon nozzle

Figure 10 : 3D carbon-carbon miscellaneous products

The 3D composite and related structures were primarily developed for space applications : reentry bodies, rocket motor nozzles (integral throat and entrance or free standing ITE design) and exit cones. They have rapidly equalled and even surpassed their counterparts produced presently in the free world. Now they are penetrating other domains such as brakes, human prostheses, pipes to carry high pressure and high temperature fluids, etc.

THE CHOPPED FIBER MULTIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE PRODUCTS

At the rear of the space motors different equipment is located such as hydraulic power supply, actuators to manoeuvre the nozzle, attitude control equipment, etc. This equipment needs to be protected from the thermal radiative flux in flight. In case of inter-stage separation by ignition of one stage before the separation itself, there is both thermal flux and rapid pressure variation during this phase. Moreover, the equipment having complex shapes the heatshields have to be easily moldable to any shape. The AQ 60 material was designed in order to manufacture heatshields capable of meeting these different stringent requirements. It is based on phenolic resin reinforced by silica fibers.

Figure 11 : Casing in AQ 60 material

The reinforcement is aspirated out of a suspension of chopped fibers in a water based liquid on a mold having the desired shape. This process is entirely automatic. The reinforcement is then postdensified by a phenolic resin. The resulting material has a very low density (0.3) as well as isolation characteristics and thermal shock resistance better than the silicon based and cork based heatshields (thermal conductivity of 0.2 to 0.35 W/m°C, ability to face a thermal flux of 20 MW/m² during 0.3 second). Although very porous (porosity up to 80 %) the material is strong enough to sustain pressure variation of 15 bars in 50 milliseconds.

Figure 12 : Workshop to manufacture automatically the chopped fibers composite products

Consequently, the potential applications of chopped fibers multidirectional composites developed at AEROSPATIALE Aquitaine are much broader than the ones developed before. We can now reach domains such as heatshields for the European space shuttle, structural antiradiative heatshields around exit cones, carbon carbon brakes, filtering units, noise absorbants, etc.

CONCLUSION

During the last three decades the space and ballistic systems industry had to develop revolutionary concepts in order to face very stringent specifications. Let's recall as an example that in order to enhance the payload, 80 % of a strategic missile is non metallic. In the preceding sections we have emphasized same examples regarding structures made with high performance composite materials : motor cases, carbon-carbon parts for reentry bodies and nozzles, very light heatshields. For a long time the aeronautical industry was a closed club. We have shown, by applying the know how developed to transportation, energy storage and marine activities that there is a real will to widen the range of activity to different domains. AEROSPATIALE is one of the European leader in this expansion effort.

